

**NEW REPORT ON COVID ORIGINS
SUPPORTS LABORATORY SOURCE
AND FINDS CONCERNING
NEUROLOGICAL IMPACTS**

A RESPONSE TO *A CRITICAL REVIEW OF COVID-19 ORIGINS:
“HIDDEN IN PLAIN SIGHT”*

OCTOBER 2025

WRITTEN BY
ROBIN ROBINSON

Scowcroft Institute
of International Affairs

THE BUSH SCHOOL

The views expressed and opinions presented in this paper are those of its author and do not necessarily reflect the positions of Texas A&M University, the Bush School of Government & Public Service, or the Scowcroft Institute of International Affairs.

Scowcroft Institute of International Affairs

THE BUSH SCHOOL

New Report on COVID Origins Supports Laboratory Source and Finds Concerning Neurological Impacts

Robin Robinson

A new report entitled *A Critical Review of COVID Origins: "Hidden in Plain Sight"* by Dr. Robert Kadlec presents the results of substantial analyses and new perspectives on the origins of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the possibility of strategic interest by the People's Republic of China in coronaviruses as neurocognitive bioweapons, and long COVID cognitive diminution and memory loss and vaccine prevention. By critically reviewing thousands of COVID-19 related published works, publicly available communications, and WHO and government reports through traditional medical, virological, and epidemiological, and forensic prisms, the study strongly supports the theory that SARS-CoV-2 virus may have been released from a lab accident at the Wuhan Institute of Virology where it had been genetically engineered from specific genes of different coronaviruses to make the virus more infectious and virulent in humans; further this analysis provides little evidence that SARS-CoV-2 evolved from natural recombination and entered the human population through a zoonotic spillover event in a Wuhan wet market.

The study provides support that (i) gain-of-function experiments on natural and recombinant coronaviruses were performed at the Wuhan Institute of Virology in 2018-2019 prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, (ii) SARS-CoV-2 virus may have resulted from genetic engineering of the Malayan pangolin coronavirus and specific genetic elements in the spike protein (i.e., human ACE-2 binding site, furin cleavage site, integrin binding motifs, etc.) amidst restriction enzyme fingerprints; (iii) the pre-pandemic development of vaccine candidates at Beijing's Academy of Military Medical Sciences (i.e., Spike RBD-Fc polypeptide+ adjuvant, full-length Spike protein in an Adenovirus-vector) utilized portions of the new recombinant coronaviruses as immunogen targets, and (iv) experiments studying the neurovirulence of natural and recombinant coronaviruses were ongoing several years before the COVID-19 pandemic, opening for debate the question of whether the emergence of the SARS-CoV-2 virus was an accidental byproduct of a state-sponsored bioweapons military program focused on introducing bioweapons that render its victim with impaired and debilitating neurocognitive functions.

The stated development timelines of COVID-19 vaccines in China with February patent filings are inconsistent with SARS-CoV-2 virus isolation and identification in January 2020. The timeline of 44 days for vaccine development at the Academy of Military Medical Sciences, specifically the time from viral genomic sequencing to a murine immunogenicity study for the SARS-CoV-2 Spike RBD + Fc tag vaccine candidate, in 2019 appears incongruous compared to the accelerated timelines demonstrated for the COVID-19 mRNA (2020) and avian influenza (2015 and 2017) vaccines by experienced laboratories and vaccine manufacturers during these crises. A timeline of 60-75 days from viral RBD+ FC tag gene cloning to demonstration of immunogenicity plus 21-28 days post-vaccination in

humanized ACE2 mice is more realistic (at least 80-100 days total); therefore, SARS-CoV-2 virus must have been present in Wuhan in fall 2019.

The study reviews newer studies on the enduring acute and chronic neurological effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection and residual sequelae resulting in long COVID and its many manifestations. Study results are cited that show COVID-19 vaccines do prevent or reduce the intensity and duration of long COVID, especially in pediatric and elderly populations; the former is experiencing alarming reductions in vaccination rate more recently. It is noteworthy that long COVID neurocognitive effects as cited in the paper exacerbate the global and U.S. dementia tsunami that will incapacitate worldwide public health, finances, and infrastructure over the next 25 years, adversely affecting global and national security. Regardless of the origin of SARS-CoV-2 viruses, the COVID-19 pandemic illustrates how precarious global emerging infectious diseases are with other biothreats like avian influenza, chikungunya, Lassa fever, and others looming.

About the Author

***Dr. Robin Robinson** is currently the CEO of Esperovax, Inc. developing oral vaccines with yeast-based circular RNA technology. He formerly served as Vaccine Director at Novavax, Inc. and the founding Director of the Biomedical Advanced Research and Development Authority (BARDA) at the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. At BARDA using a public-private partnership model, he led hundreds of early-stage product candidates through advanced clinical and manufacturing development resulting in more than 60 FDA-approved and marketed products.*

The views expressed and opinions presented in this paper are those of its author and do not necessarily reflect the positions of Texas A&M University, the Bush School of Government & Public Service, or the Scowcroft Institute of International Affairs.

Scowcroft Institute of International Affairs

THE BUSH SCHOOL